

Consumer awareness and market trends in OTC drugs and food supplements: a 10-year comparative study in Bulgaria

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Abstract

This study identifies a significant shift in consumer trust toward healthcare professionals, particularly physicians, as key influencers in the selection of OTC drugs and food supplements ($\chi^2 = 10.88$, $p \leq 0.01$). Trust in pharmacists remained stable over the decade ($\chi^2 = 0.10$, $p \geq 0.05$). In 2023, 68.0% of respondents reported using supplements only when needed, compared to 34.3% in 2013 ($\chi^2 = 38.2$, $p \leq 0.001$), indicating more rational use. Nearly half (49.1%) acknowledged that some supplements may pose health risks. These findings underscore the need for enhanced regulatory oversight and targeted communication strategies to combat misinformation, manage risk perception, and support evidence-based self-medication.

Keywords

OTC products; food supplements; patient awareness; safety; self-medication

Introduction

The term ‘over-the-counter’ refers to products that can be purchased without a doctor’s prescription and are widely available in pharmacies, supermarkets, or online (Petkova and Hadzhieva 2021). The market for food supplements and over-the-counter (OTC) drugs has shown significant global growth. The increasing use of OTC drugs and self-care is determined by socio-economic factors, including lifestyle, accessibility of medications, and rising health awareness (Todorova 2015; Petkova et al. 2023). This expansion is driven by an increase in public interest in health following the COVID-19 pandemic, along with advances in diagnostic and preventive healthcare practices (IQVIA Bulgaria 2023). A particularly notable trend is the increase in online sales of vitamins, minerals, and food

supplements, with projections indicating that the volume of online trade in such products will triple between 2018 and 2025 (CRN 2022; Hadzhieva et al. 2022).

In 2023, Bulgaria’s pharmaceutical market recorded substantial growth, with total sales increasing by 14.7% to reach €2.7 billion. Oncology therapies have emerged as the leading category in hospital drug sales. The pharmacy retail segment, which represents approximately 75% of the national market, also showed strong performance, growing by 11.3% in value (Kotseva and Nikolov 2024). The Bulgarian food supplement market, dominated by probiotics, immunostimulants, and joint care products, also saw notable growth, with pharmacy sales reaching nearly €419 million in 2023. Sales of slimming products followed an upward trend, and online pharmacy purchases increased significantly, registering a 28% increase.

According to current pharmaceutical legislation, only non-prescription drugs, cosmetics, nutritional supplements, medical supplies, dietary foods, and baby food can be sold online. Among these, the top-selling items include vitamins, analgesics, and cosmetic products (Kotseva and Nikolov 2024).

Despite their perceived benefits, the uncontrolled use of food supplements and OTC drugs carries significant risks. Although self-treatment with such products offers certain medical and economic advantages, inappropriate selection or incorrect dosing may result in serious adverse health outcomes (Hadzhieva and Petkova-Dimitrova 2024). The active ingredients in these products can have substantial physiological effects, and the popular belief that “natural” equals “safe” often results in disregard for appropriate dosing and possible drug interactions (FDA 2022). Documented cases reveal that some patients unilaterally replace prescribed medications with food supplements, potentially compromising therapeutic outcomes and increasing the risk of complications (Singh et al. 2021).

Regulatory approaches to OTC drugs and food supplements vary significantly between countries. In several European nations, OTC products can be sold outside licensed pharmacies (for example, in supermarkets and petrol stations), which facilitates self-medication but raises concerns about consumer safety (Singh et al. 2021). In the United States, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) regulates dietary supplements under the Dietary Supplement Health and Education Act (DSHEA) (FDA 1994) and the OTC Monograph System, placing the responsibility for safety and labelling on manufacturers. In the European Union, food supplements are regulated by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) (European Food Safety Authority 2024) under Directive 2002/46/EC (EUR-Lex 2002) and Regulation (EC) No 1924/2006, with enforcement delegated to national authorities (EUR-Lex 2006). In Bulgaria, these responsibilities are shared by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (BFSA) (<https://bfsa.egov.bg/wps/portal/bfsa-web/home>) for food supplements and the Bulgarian Drug Agency (BDA) for OTC drugs (Bulgarian Drug Agency 2025b), as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Regulatory authorities by region.

Region/Country	Regulatory authority (food supplements)	Regulatory authority (OTC)	Main regulations
USA	FDA	FDA	DSHEA
			OTC monograph system
EU	European Commission and national authorities	EMA and national authorities 1924/2006	Directive 2002/46/EC Regulation (EC) No
Bulgaria	BFSA	BDA	Food law
			Medicinal products in human
			Medicine act

A study investigating the role of real-world data (RWD) and real-world evidence (RWE) in the reclassification of prescription-only medicines (Rx) to OTC status emphasises the importance of transparency in regulatory

evaluation processes. The application of RWD and RWE varies between countries such as Germany, the United States, and the United Kingdom, resulting in differing regulatory decisions. Clearly defined criteria and procedures significantly increase the likelihood of an OTC product being approved. Among these, safety remains the paramount factor in reassessing regulatory status. It is essential not only to establish pharmacological safety but also to demonstrate that consumers can use the product correctly and safely without supervision (EMA 2023).

Regulation and use of food supplements and OTC drugs require a balanced approach—one that ensures access to safe and effective products while mitigating misuse. Enhancing consumer awareness and ensuring transparency in regulatory processes are critical to safeguarding public health. Within the European regulatory context, Bulgaria adheres to the overarching legal framework; however, more efforts are needed to align national control mechanisms with evolving public health needs and the dynamics of the modern pharmaceutical marketplace. The aim of this study is to analyse the evolution of consumer attitudes and awareness regarding the use of OTC drugs and food supplements within the framework of regulatory developments and market dynamics in Bulgaria.

Materials and methods

Study design and setting

The study was conducted between April and May 2023 in community pharmacies located in the city of Sofia, Bulgaria. A direct, anonymous questionnaire was administered to individuals requesting OTC drugs and food supplements. Participation was entirely voluntary and anonymous, with no incentives offered to respondents.

Survey instrument

The structured questionnaire consisted of three sections: (1) questions regarding the selection and use of OTC products and food supplements; (2) questions identifying the factors influencing consumer choice; and (3) general demographic information. The face validity of the instrument was reviewed and confirmed by three academic experts in social pharmacy.

Sample size

A total of 162 participants were randomly selected at the point of sale in community pharmacies. Inclusion criteria included being of legal age and requesting an OTC product or dietary supplement at the time of recruitment.

Comparative analysis

To assess trends over time, the results of the 2023 survey were compared to those of a previous study conducted

by the same research team in 2013 (Tsvetkova 2015). The earlier survey included 172 respondents from the city of Varna and employed a comparable methodology and questionnaire structure, enabling meaningful longitudinal analysis.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistical methods were applied to summarise and analyse the survey data. To assess differences in consumer behaviour between 2013 and 2023, a chi-square (χ^2) test of independence was used to determine statistical significance between categorical variables.

Microsoft Excel (version 2019) was utilised for data entry and statistical processing. Results are presented in tabular format, highlighting percentage distributions and χ^2 -test values with corresponding significance levels (p values).

Results

Table 2 presents the results of a comparative analysis of changes in consumer behaviour between 2013 and 2023. Statistically significant differences between the two periods were identified based on χ^2 tests.

Table 2. Comparative analysis of consumer behaviour related to OTC drugs and food supplements (2013 vs. 2023).

Factors/Questions	2013 (%)	2023 (%)	χ^2 -test result	Change
Factors influencing consumer choice				
Physicians	18.6	33.9	10.88**	Significant increase
Pharmacists	24.42	23.2	0.10	NS
Internet	4.65	12.0	4.45*	Significant increase
TV/Radio advertising	8.14	5.0	1.54	NS
Friends/Acquaintances	2.33	8.9	5.92*	Significant increase
Frequency of use				
Only when needed	34.3	68.0	38.2***	Significant increase
Regular use	33.8	23.0	4.8*	Significant decrease
Do not use	32.0	9.0	26.7***	Significant decrease
Reading product brochures				
Always read a brochure	33.72	18	10.27**	Significant decrease
Never read a brochure	33.72	11	23.6***	Significant decrease

Significance levels: * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$; *** $p \leq 0.001$; NS = Not significant ($p \geq 0.05$).

Factors influencing consumer choice

The findings reveal significant shifts in consumer behaviour related to sources of information and guidance in selecting OTC drugs and food supplements over the past decade. Notably, trust in physicians has increased substantially. In 2013, 18.6% of respondents reported that physicians influenced their choice of products, compared to 33.9% in 2023 – a statistically significant increase ($\chi^2 = 10.88$, $p \leq 0.01$). This trend suggests a growing reliance on medical expertise in self-care decision-making. In parallel, reliance on digital sources – particularly the Internet – also demonstrated a statistically significant rise. The proportion of respondents identifying the Internet as a

primary influence increased from 4.65% in 2013 to 12.0% in 2023 ($\chi^2 = 4.45$, $p \leq 0.05$), reflecting broader digitalisation trends in health information-seeking behaviour. In contrast, the influence of pharmacists remained relatively stable over the ten-year period. In 2013, 24.42% of respondents cited pharmacists as a key source of information, compared to 23.2% in 2023, with no statistically significant difference observed ($\chi^2 = 0.10$, $p \geq 0.05$). This stability underscores the enduring trust placed in pharmacists as accessible healthcare professionals. Additionally, the influence of friends and acquaintances increased significantly, from 2.33% in 2013 to 8.9% in 2023 ($\chi^2 = 5.92$, $p \leq 0.05$), highlighting the growing impact of peer networks and informal communication channels on consumer decision-making.

Patterns of food supplement use

Substantial changes were also observed in the frequency and manner of food supplement consumption. In 2023, 68.0% of respondents reported using food supplements only when needed, compared to 34.3% in 2013 – representing a statistically significant twofold increase ($\chi^2 = 38.2$, $p \leq 0.001$). This shift suggests a more selective and rational approach to supplement use. Conversely, regular or daily use declined significantly over the same period, from 33.8% in 2013 to 23.0% in 2023 ($\chi^2 = 4.8$, $p \leq 0.05$), indicating a movement away from habitual or potentially excessive consumption. Furthermore, the proportion of respondents who reported not using supplements at all decreased markedly – from 32.0% in 2013 to just 9.0% in 2023 ($\chi^2 = 26.7$, $p \leq 0.001$). This trend points to increased accessibility, social acceptance, and integration of supplements into broader health maintenance behaviours.

Engagement with product information leaflets

Consumer engagement with product brochures (leaflets) also changed significantly over the ten-year period. In 2023, only 18.0% of respondents reported actively reading the brochures, a substantial decline from 33.72% in 2013 ($\chi^2 = 10.27$, $p \leq 0.01$). Similarly, the proportion of individuals who reported never reading product brochures also decreased, from 33.72% in 2013 to 11.0% in 2023 – a statistically significant change ($\chi^2 = 23.6$, $p \leq 0.001$).

The data presented in Table 3 pertain to two questions that were included exclusively in the 2023 survey; however, they are interpreted within the broader context of the study's overall objectives.

Purchasing channel preferences

Survey data indicate that the overwhelming majority of respondents (82.7%, $n = 134$) prefer to purchase OTC drugs and food supplements from a pharmacy, reinforcing the dominant role of traditional retail channels. Among these, 69.1% ($n = 112$) reported that their preference is based on

Table 3. Consumer preferences and risk perceptions related to OTC drugs and food supplements (N = 162).

Consumer preferences for channels of purchasing OTC drugs and food supplements	
Pharmacy	82.7% (n = 134)
I prefer a pharmacist's opinion	69.1% (n = 112)
I can start taking the product immediately	11.7% (n = 19)
No risk of confusing the supplement	1.8% (n = 3)
Internet	15.4% (n = 25)
It's discreet	1.8% (n = 3)
I don't wait in line at the pharmacy	5.5% (n = 9)
I can compare prices across websites and choose the most costeffective option	8.1% (n = 13)
Other	1.8% (n = 3)
Perceptions of health risks associated with food supplements	
Some supplements pose a health risk	49.1% (n = 79)
I don't know	35.1% (n = 57)
No supplement poses a health risk	15.8% (n = 26)
All supplements pose a health risk	0%

the opportunity to consult with a pharmacist, suggesting a high level of trust in professional guidance. Other motivations for choosing a pharmacy include the possibility of immediate product use (11.7%, n = 19) and the perceived safety in avoiding confusion between products (1.8%, n = 3). In contrast, 15.4% of respondents (n = 25) reported purchasing from internet-based sources. Within this group, the most cited reasons included the ability to compare prices across websites and find cost-effective options (8.1%, n = 13), avoiding queues in physical pharmacies (5.5%, n = 9), and ensuring discretion during the purchasing process (1.8%, n = 3). An additional 1.8% (n = 3) indicated other unspecified reasons for their channel selection.

Perceptions of health risks associated with food supplements

When asked about the potential health risks of food supplements, nearly half of respondents (49.1%, n = 79) acknowledged that some supplements may pose health risks, indicating a relatively high level of risk awareness. A considerable proportion (35.1%, n = 57) expressed uncertainty, selecting "I don't know" as their response, which may reflect gaps in health literacy or inconsistent information in the public domain. Only 15.8% (n = 26) believed that no supplement poses a health risk, and none of the respondents stated that all supplements pose a health risk.

Discussion

This study highlights a significant shift in consumer trust toward healthcare professionals, particularly physicians, as key influencers in the selection of OTC drugs and food supplements. This development may be interpreted as a positive trend that supports the safer and more rational use of such products. In support of this, Mangarov and co-authors (2025) state that the patient-physician relationship is a core element of healthcare, characterised by vulnerability and trust, and represents one of the most

significant human interactions shaped by both subjective and objective factors. Similarly, the consistently high trust in pharmacists suggests enduring confidence in pharmaceutical expertise and underscores the continued relevance of face-to-face consultations in consumer decision-making. In modern society, the role of pharmacists in the provision of medicines, dietary supplements, and OTC products is becoming increasingly important due to the abundance of health information, the growing practice of self-medication, and the use of non-prescription products (Ivanova et al. 2022). Alongside these traditional sources, a growing reliance on digital platforms was also observed. The increasing influence of the internet and social networks likely reflects the lasting impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, which substantially altered patterns of communication and access to health information. This shift underscores the rising importance of informal peer networks and online communities, where personal experiences and anecdotal evidence increasingly shape consumer decisions. Collectively, these findings suggest the need for integrated communication strategies that bridge both conventional channels (e.g. physicians and pharmacists) and digital media (e.g. websites and social platforms) to support informed, evidence-based choices.

The ten-year comparison revealed substantial changes in the patterns of supplement use. The sharp rise in "as-needed" use suggests a transition toward more situational and informed decision-making. Conversely, regular use declined significantly, indicating reduced habitual consumption. These trends may reflect improved public awareness, greater scrutiny in self-care practices, and easier access to guidance from healthcare professionals. International findings appear to corroborate this development. For instance, the CRN Consumer Survey reported the highest level of dietary supplement use in the past two decades, with 77% of the U.S. population declaring regular or occasional use (CRN 2022). Such trends support the notion that dietary supplements have become increasingly integrated into public health behaviours across various regions.

Engagement with product brochures remains a key indicator of health literacy, particularly regarding allergen awareness, correct dosage, and storage instructions. However, data from 2023 show a statistically significant decline in both full engagement and total disregard for these materials compared to 2013. This dual decrease suggests a behavioural shift toward partial or selective reading, possibly in favour of alternative sources such as online platforms and peer recommendations. This trend is consistent with earlier findings indicating that while product leaflets serve as a primary information source, they are often underutilised. Despite the rise of digital alternatives, previous research confirms that printed educational tools remain among the most reliable and accessible methods for conveying essential safety information, particularly for individuals with limited e-health literacy (Bernier and Yasko 1991).

According to data from the National Statistical Institute, 17.1% of Bulgarian consumers purchased medicines, supplements, or vitamins online in 2023, rising to 19.3%

in 2024 (National Statistical Institute 2024). However, social networks, although widely used, cannot substitute for the individualised consultation and professional expertise provided by pharmacists and physicians. These findings suggest a growing need for a multi-channel approach that balances trust, cost-efficiency, and convenience in healthcare communication and product delivery.

Nearly half of the respondents (49.1%) acknowledged that some supplements pose health risks, while 35.1% were uncertain. This distribution suggests that most consumers adopt a balanced view, recognising potential risks without overgeneralising. The growing reliance on informal sources and the mixed levels of awareness indicate that digital literacy does not necessarily equate to informed decision-making. Findings by Slavchev (2021) support this view, noting that many consumers underestimate the risks associated with OTC products. These results underscore the need for targeted educational campaigns that emphasise both the benefits and potential adverse effects of supplement use. Public awareness initiatives should address common misconceptions and promote risk literacy through both traditional and digital media. Despite the widespread availability of information online, the accuracy and completeness of content – particularly related to side effects, contraindications, and drug interactions – remain variable. Health communication efforts should ensure that consumers have access to reliable, evidence-based information and are able to distinguish it from unverified online content. Since the implementation of Directive 2010/84/EU in July 2012, Bulgarian patients have played an active role in the pharmacovigilance system. Individuals are entitled to report adverse drug reactions directly to the Bulgarian Drug Agency (BDA), even without prior notification to a healthcare provider (EUR-Lex 2010; Bulgarian Drug Agency 2025a). In 2020, following the adoption of Bulgaria's new Food Law, regulatory oversight of supplements and OTC products has been reinforced through a specific registration regime monitored by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (BFSA) (Bulgarian Food Safety Agency 2025). These developments support a more structured and transparent approach to market regulation, which aligns with broader efforts to promote safe and informed use.

Conclusion

This study provides a detailed analysis of the evolution of consumer attitudes and awareness of food supplements and OTC drugs over a decade marked by dynamic changes in healthcare policy, patient behaviour, and digital access to health information (2013–2023). The findings corroborate previous studies suggesting a shift toward consumer-driven self-care behaviour, focusing on occasional rather than routine use of dietary supplements. This trend may be interpreted as a marker of improved individual health literacy and greater health consciousness.

The comparative analysis reveals that preventive use remains the predominant motivation, reflecting a

growing emphasis on disease prevention and long-term well-being. Furthermore, trust in healthcare professionals, particularly physicians and pharmacists, remains strong, underscoring the critical role of pharmacist consultation in public health strategies for the safe use of OTC products.

Despite these encouraging developments, the results highlight the persistent need for increased public health education, regulatory transparency, and patient empowerment. This research underscores the need for harmonised national policies aligned with European regulatory standards to support rational use and ensure consumer protection. Enhancing regulatory oversight, combined with effective communication strategies, will be essential to address misinformation, manage risk perception, and promote evidence-based self-medication.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Medical University of Varna.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

A. Tsvetkova conceived and designed the study, contributed to data collection, data analysis, and statistical evaluation and led the writing of the manuscript. D. Dimitrova assisted with data acquisition, contributed to the initial draft of the article. S. Mihaylova critically reviewed and revised the manuscript, provided insights on the discussion, and ensured the accuracy of the findings presented.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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